

MODELING OF HIGH-VELOCITY IMPACT BEHAVIOUR OF SANDWICH STRUCTURES UNDER BIRD STRIKE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC) foam-core based sandwiches with fibre-reinforced composite face sheets provide high strength and bending stiffness as well as good designability, which has been widely used in the manufacturing of transportation vehicles. While these sandwich composite structures may expose to bird strike during the service, which threatens the safety operation of high-speed transportation vehicles. The present studies combine experimental and numerical investigations on the bird-strike resistance of large-size foam-core sandwich composite structures. Gas-gun tests have been carried out to study the behaviours of foam-core sandwich composite structures subjected to an impact by gelatine projectiles. A high-speed camera is employed to capture the deformation of the projectiles and strain gauges are employed to measure the local strain near to the striking point from the rear surface of the specimens. A Finite Element (FE) model is developed to simulate the gelatine-impact on the foam-core sandwich composite structures. The constitutive model of the gelatine is built up using the Smooth Particle Hydrodynamic (SPH) method with the Murnaghan Equation Of State (EOS) for solid element. Foam-core material is modelled using the crushable foam model with isotropic hardening. Regarding the model for composite panel, an in-house subroutine has been employed, which takes account for the strain rate dependency as well as different failure modes. The Finite Element (FE) predicted deformations are compared with the ones experimentally measured by Digital Image Correlation (DIC). Good agreement has been obtained between the Finite Element (FE) predictions and experimental results. The dynamic responses and failure characteristics of the foam-core sandwich composite structures are further studied using the validated numerical model. This piece of work is able to provide some guidance to the design of the bird-strike resistant foam-core sandwich composite structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite sandwich structures are a class of composite materials combining stiff composite skins with a lightweight, low density core. This results in a structure with very high bending stiffness and low structural weight with widespread applications in aerospace [1-3]. However, both monolithic and sandwich structured composites are quite prone to high-velocity impact events. One common and major importance threat in aviation is the bird strike, which can occur during the aircraft take-off, landing or low-altitude flight [4, 5]. Therefore, it is of great significance to investigate the dynamic mechanical response of composite sandwich structure under bird strike and establish the finite element model of soft body high-velocity impact of composite sandwich structure. In the current studies, there are relatively few experimental studies on large-size composite sandwich structures under bird strike and the numerical simulation of composite sandwich structure under bird strike also needs further discussion [6-8].

In this study, the dynamic response of foam-core sandwich composite structures subjected to soft body oblique impact is investigated numerically and experimentally. The bird strike test was conducted on a gas gun employing the 3D DIC technique and strain gauges. Meanwhile, a Finite Element (FE) model is developed to simulate the gelatine-impact on the foam-core sandwich composite structures. Comparing with experimental results and numerical results in terms of the local strain near to the striking point, the model was verified. Subsequently, the matrix damage, the contact force and the displacement-time histories of the front and back face-panel were predicted.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The schematic of the bird strike experimental set-up is shown in Fig. 1. According to the take-off and landing speed of aircraft and the conditions of being potential threat by birds, the impact velocity and impact angle of bird strike test are set as 77m/s and 40°, respectively.

A 3D DIC system is used to measure the deformation of the rear-face of the specimen during impact loading. And on the side of the impact view, another high-speed camera is used to observe the entire impact process. Six strain gauges are placed near the striking point at the rear-face of the specimen.

The gelatine projectile was prepared by China aircraft strength research institute, which has a density of 960kg/m³ and a weight of 500g. Foam-core sandwich composite structures is 1000 mm in length, 700 mm in width and about 35 mm in thickness, and consists of two quasi-isotropic lay-up Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastics (CFRP) faces with 4.48mm and a 30 mm thick PVC foam-core, shown in Fig. 2. In order to enhance the bird-strike resistance of the foam-core sandwich composite structures, while satisfying the lightweight design, the lay-up of composite panels is shown in Table 1.

Fig. 1 Experimental set-up for the gas gun bird strike test employing the 3D digital image correlation (DIC) technique.

Fig. 2 Schematic of foam-core sandwich composite structure.

3 FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATION MODEL

3.1 Constitutive model for the bird

Generally speaking, the bird can be thought of as a uniform jet of fluid hitting a structure in high speed. Therefore, it can be use an EOS to model the bird material, which is given by,

$$p = p_0 + B \left[\left(\rho / \rho_0 \right)^\gamma - 1 \right]$$
, where p is a pressure, p_0 is a reference pressure, B and γ are constants to be determined, and ρ / ρ_0 is the ratio of the current mass density to the initial mass density. In this model, $B = 145$ MPa and $\gamma = 7.98$ [9].

3.2 Constitutive model for the foam-core

The foam-core is modeled as an elastic-plastic material. The elastic part of the response of the foam-core was defined as ELASTIC ISOTROPIC. The plastic part of the response of the foam-core is modeled using the CRUSHABLE FOAM and the CRUSHABLE FOAM HARDENING options. The material parameters and hardening parameters of foam-core are shown in Ref [2].

3.3 Composite damage model

The composite panel is modeled as elastic material, with parameters which are presented in Ref [10]. The panels failure criteria proposed by Hashin criteria to detect the failure modes in the matrix and fibre under both tension and compression failures.

The failure modes included in Hashin's criteria are as follows:

$$(1) \text{ Fibre failure in tension } (\sigma_{11} \geq 0): \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_T} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_{12}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{13}}{S_{13}} \right)^2 \geq 1$$

$$(2) \text{ Fibre failure in compression } (\sigma_{11} < 0): \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_C} \right)^2 \geq 1$$

$$(3) \text{ Matrix failure in tension } (\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33} \geq 0):$$

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{Y_T} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_{12}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{13}}{S_{13}} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{S_{23}^2} (\sigma_{23}^2 - \sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}) \geq 1$$

$$(4) \text{ Matrix failure in compression } (\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33} < 0):$$

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{2S_{23}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_{12}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{13}}{S_{13}} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{S_{23}^2} (\sigma_{23}^2 - \sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}) + \frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{Y_C} \left[\left(\frac{Y_C}{2S_{23}} \right)^2 - 1 \right] \geq 1$$

where, σ_{ij} ($i, j=1,2,3$) represents effective stress tensor, X_T , X_C , Y_T , Y_C are the tensile and compressive strengths of composites along to and perpendicular to the longitudinal direction, respectively. S_{12} , S_{13} , S_{23} are shear strengths in the three directions, respectively.

3.4 The finite element model of the bird strike

The FE model is established for the gelatine projectile, the composite panels and the foam-core in ABAQUS/CAE, in Fig. 3. The bird geometry is as a cylinder: $D=94\text{mm}$, $h=72\text{mm}$ (Fig. 3a). Foam-core sandwich composite structure have a dimension of $1000\text{mm} \times 700\text{mm} \times 35\text{mm}$. Composite plies and foam-core are meshed using eight-node linear hexahedral elements with reduced integration and hourglass control (C3D8R). A refined zone of $500 \times 350 \text{ mm}$ is created with an element size of $1 \text{ mm} \times 1 \text{ mm}$ (Fig. 3b). The contact interaction between all surfaces is modeled by the general contact. In addition, the composite panels and the foam core are connected by "tie". The clamping boundary condition is set for the whole foam-core sandwich composite structure. Fig. 3c shows the finite element model of the soft body oblique high-velocity impact.

Fig. 3 The finite element model of the bird strike experiment: (a) the model of percussive bird; (b) the mesh of the impact plate; (d) the impact test with angle 40° .

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Experimental results of bird strike

The process of bird strike test was captured by a high-speed camera, as shown in Fig. 4. The entire impacting process lasted about 3.0 ms. $T = 0$ is the instant when the gelatine made contact with the plate. Pictures of $T = 0.4$ ms to $T = 1.6$ ms show that the gelatine first impacted the plate and was then gradually crushed. Eventually, the gelatine projectile was torn into debris by the high impact pressure and the debris flowed outwards from the contact point on the plate surface. During all the impacting process, no damage or failure was observed on the plate.

Fig. 4 Gelatine impacting process at impact angle 40° with velocity 77m/s.

Fig. 5a shows the dynamic major displacement contours obtained from the 3D DIC system, used to measure the deformation of the rear-face of the specimen, during impact loading. With the contact

between the gelatine projectile and the plate, the displacement contours are circular and gradually increases. In contrast to the high-velocity impact of a hard object, the gelatine quickly changes into a fluid shape, disperses over the impact surface and bounces. Thus, during the final phase of the impact event, the displacement contours become elliptical, followed by repeated vibration. Fig. 5b presents the out-of-plane displacement of the central point for the rear-face of the foam-core sandwich composite structure. The maximum out-of-plane deformation for this specimen is ca. 22.5 mm.

Fig. 5 Experimental results (obtained from 3D DIC) for the foam-core sandwich composite structure impacted at a velocity of 77 m s^{-1} for the: (a) full-field out-of-plane displacement; (b) the central, maximum, out-of-plane displacement as a function of time.

Fig. 6 displays the experimental results of strains on the rear-face of the plate about 305mm away from the impact center point in the diagonal. The results show that a pair of strain values (between transverse and longitudinal) at b and c have great differences. This may be due to the fact that during impact, when the gelatine projectile hits the plate, its trajectory tends to region b. The transverse strain value collected by strain gauge 3# is initially negative. At the same time, the impact should make the lateral change at C larger.

Compared with the strain-time curve from the strain gauge data measured in bird strike test and DIC data, as shown in Fig. 7, the results are consistent well. This indicates that DIC results in the experiment are credible.

Fig. 6 Strain-time curves of experimental results.

Fig. 7 Consistency of strain gauge and DIC results.

4.2 Numerical results of bird strike model

Fig. 8 plots the strain-time curve of the simulation results with the experimental measurements. The numerical results give the best agreement with the experimental data, including the trend and the peak value. As shown in Fig. 9, the deformation contours on the rear-face of the plate are presented. It can be seen that the numerical predictions are in good agreement with the DIC results. The contour gradually changes from circular to oval.

Therefore, the model can be effectively used to study the dynamic responses and failure characteristics of the foam-core sandwich composite structure during bird strike.

Fig. 8 Comparison of the strain from the experiments and the modelling.

The matrix damage of the specimen are predicted in Fig. 10. No obvious surface damage and fracture occurred in the foam-core sandwich composite structure specimen. Only the first two layers of the carbon fibre composite panel have matrix damage. Moreover, in the rear-face of the carbon fibre composite panel in the Z direction, only about 0.9mm of permanent deformation occurs. For large-scale foam-core sandwich composite structure, this is a very slight deformation.

Fig. 9 Numerical predictions on the displacement contours for the rear-face of plate during the 40° oblique impact process.

Fig. 10 Matrix damage obtained from the first two layers of composite panels by numerical simulations.

Further, the variations of the contact force and strain as a function of time on the specimen, shown in Fig. 11, reveal that both the strain and the force exhibit the same deformation trend in the material at the same specific time. Evident also is the residual strain in the back face panel after impact. The residual strains on the back surface of the panel indicate some damage [10].

Fig. 11 Variation of contact force and strain as a function of time.

Fig. 12 Displacement-time histories of the front and back face-panels for all configurations.

Fig. 12 depicts the displacement-time histories of the front and back face panel among the different configurations. Due to the cushioning effect of the foam-core material, the displacement of the back face panel of the sandwich structure is smaller than that of the front back face-panel [11]. However, it may be due to it is an oblique impact, the displacement difference is not obvious.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In the study, the bird-strike resistance of the large-scale foam-core sandwich composite structures were investigated experimentally and numerically. Gas-gun tests with a digital image correlation (DIC) system and strain gauges were employed to study the behaviours of foam-core sandwich composite structures subjected to gelatine impact. A finite element model was developed to simulate the gelatine impact on the foam-core sandwich composite structures. The dynamic responses and failure characteristics of the foam-core sandwich composite structures were predicted using the predictive model consisting of constitutive models of gelatine, foam-core and CFRP.

During the simulative bird strike tests, the gelatine projectile was torn into debris by the high impact pressure and the debris flowed outwards from the contact region on the plate surface. The deformation contours and the relationship between strain and time were obtained by DIC system and strain gauges. The contour gradually changed from circular to oval shape. The maximum out-of-plane deformation for this specimen is ca. 22.5 mm. Moreover, the strain-gauge measured strains were greatly affected by the distance between the measuring point and the impact point, shown as the strain-gauge with larger distance delivered a larger strain value. Simulation results showed that only the first two layers of the carbon fibre composite panel have matrix damage, and the permanent displacement deformation is very small. A good agreement was obtained between the modelling results and the experimental results. In addition, the strain versus time traces and the force versus time traces exhibited similar deformation trends during the monitored time period. In addition, the permanent deformation was observed on the rear skin of post-impacted specimens, which is deemed to be caused by the damage occurred during the strike process. This research is expected to provide a better understanding of failure mechanisms of sandwich composite structures subjected bird-strike loading.

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